

POST-FIRE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BURNT SANDWICH COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

A thermal-mechanical model for calculating the residual stiffness and strength of burnt sandwich composite structures following fire exposure is presented. The model computes the unsteady-state heat flow and decomposition of a sandwich composite exposed to one-sided radiant heating representative of a fire scenario. The model also computes the residual tensile and compressive properties of a fire-damaged sandwich composite at room temperature. The accuracy of the model is assessed using post-fire stiffness and failure stress property data for a sandwich composite beam consisting of face skins of E-glass/vinyl ester laminate and a core of balsa wood. Experimental testing reveals that the residual tensile and compressive properties of the sandwich composite decrease rapidly due mainly to thermal decomposition to the fire-exposed skin. The model can accurately predict the residual stiffness and strength properties of fire-damaged sandwich composites. The model reveals that the post-fire tensile properties are controlled by char damage to the entire sandwich composite whereas the post-fire compressive properties are only dependent on charring to the front skin, resulting in inferior residual stiffness and strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

A problem with using sandwich composites in structural applications is poor fire resistance [1]. The polymer matrix to the laminate skins will decompose, ignite and burn when exposed to high temperature fire. Similarly, organic core materials used in sandwich composites (e.g. polymer foam, syntactic foam, Nomex, balsa wood) are flammable. Fire is a major threat to the application of sandwich composites used in aircraft, ships, civil infrastructure, offshore platform and other uses. Without adequate fire protection, sandwich composites can rapidly ignite with the release of large amounts of heat (which adds to the fuel load), smoke and potentially toxic fumes [2-6]. Sandwich composites can also weaken and fail due to thermal softening and decomposition of the skins and core. It is a critical safety issue that sandwich structures are designed to survive a specified fire hazard (e.g. ISO834 cellulosic fire or UL1709 hydrocarbon fire conditions) without posing a threat to safety and without excessive back surface heating or failure.

Assessing the fire structural performance and survivability of sandwich composites is reliant on modelling and experimental testing. Many models have been developed to predict the thermal-mechanical response of sandwich composites in fire. The models consider the case of a flat sandwich panel under combined mechanical loading and one-sided uniform heating representative of fire. The models are capable of predicting the temperature rise in the sandwich composite and the resultant reduction to the mechanical properties. However, the models are only valid for computing the softening and failure of sandwich composite in fire. The models are not valid for burnt sandwich composites whereby the fire has been extinguished and the material has cooled to ambient temperature.

The capability to predict the residual mechanical properties of sandwich composites following fire is needed. Determining the post-fire properties is key to evaluating the structural integrity and safety of heat-affected and burnt sandwich composites following fire. Mouritz and Gardiner [7] developed a model to calculate the post-fire compressive stiffness and strength of polymer foam core sandwich composites that fail by either core shear cracking or front skin buckling. The work by Gardiner and Mouritz revealed that the extent of decomposition (char) through the sandwich composite is the damage controlling the post-fire compressive properties. Ulven and Vaidya [8] experimentally assessed the effect of fire on the impact response of sandwich composite materials. Apart from these two studies, the post-fire mechanical properties of sandwich composites have not been studied. However, there is a large body of modelling and experimental research into the post-fire mechanical properties of fibre reinforced polymer laminates [9-15], which can be relevant to the post-fire properties of the laminate skins to sandwich composites.

This paper presents a thermal-mechanical model for calculating the post-fire mechanical properties of sandwich composites. The thermal component of the model computes the heat conduction through the sandwich composite and the resultant thermal decomposition (charring) to the skins and core. The mechanical component calculates the residual stiffness and strength properties of the fire-damaged sandwich composite based on the amount of charring. The accuracy of the model is assessed using post-fire tensile and compressive property data for a sandwich composite consisting of woven glass/vinyl ester laminate skins and balsa wood core. This material was selected because of its use in naval ship structures such as the superstructure and hull, where ship-board fire is a major risk.

2 POST-FIRE MODEL FOR SANDWICH COMPOSITES

A model to calculate the post-fire mechanical properties involves thermal, decomposition and mechanical analysis of sandwich composites with organic skins and core. The model involves three main analytical steps: (1) thermal analysis, (2) decomposition analysis and (3) post-fire property analysis. The first step involves thermal analysis to calculate the through-thickness temperatures of the sandwich composite when exposed to a one-side thermal flux radiated by fire. The second step involves computing the amount of through-thickness decomposition (char formation) to the skins and core, which is based on the thermal analysis. The final step involves the use of mechanical models to calculate reductions to the post-fire tensile and compressive properties of the sandwich composite, which is based on the decomposition analysis. It is assumed with the model that the reduction to the post-fire properties is caused solely by char formation.

Thermal Analysis of Sandwich Composite

Thermal analysis of the sandwich composite exposed to one-sided radiant heating representative of a possible fire scenario is based on the model developed by Feih et al. [16]. A full description of the model is given in Ref [16], and therefore it is only briefly described here. The thermal analysis assumes that the sandwich composite is uniformly heated over one skin, and heat transfer only occurs in the through-thickness direction (and not in the lateral and transverse directions). The one-dimensional governing equation to calculate the temperature rise with heating time ($\partial T / \partial t$) in the front skin (exposed directly to the fire), core and back skin are calculated using the equations [16]:

$$\text{Skins: } \rho_{(s)} C_{p(s)} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k_{x(s)} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} - \dot{m}_g C_{pg(s)} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} (Q_{(s)} + h_{solid(s)} - h_{gas(s)}) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Core: } \rho_{(c)} C_{p(c)} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k_{x(c)} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} - \dot{m}_g C_{pg(c)} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} (Q_{(c)} + h_{solid(c)} - h_{gas(c)}) \quad (2)$$

The subscripts s and c refer to the skins and core, respectively. ρ is the density. k_x and C_p are the through-thickness thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity, respectively. \dot{m}_g is the mass flux of volatiles from the decomposition zone in the sandwich composite towards the fire exposed surface. C_{pg} is the specific heat capacity of volatiles. Q is the endothermic decomposition energy of the laminate skins ($Q_{(s)}$) or core material ($Q_{(c)}$).

The thermal model makes several important assumptions about the thermal behaviour of a sandwich composite in fire. Firstly, the model is a one-dimensional equation that only analyses conductive heat transfer and mass transport of decomposition gases in the through-thickness direction. Heat conduction and gas flow in the lateral and transverse directions of the sandwich composite are assumed not to occur because the material is evenly heated over one surface. Secondly, it is assumed that heat-induced delaminations, skin-core interfacial cracking and other types of damage to the sandwich composite during the decomposition and failure processes do not alter the thermal conductivity or gas flow. It is also assumed that the temperature is only dependent on heat conduction, gas flow and decomposition, and other processes (e.g. internal pressures, thermal-induced or force-induced strains) have no effect.

The thermal boundary condition on the hot skin is assumed to be a constant thermal flux. The model can consider any thermal boundary condition for the back skin surface. In this study the back skin is assumed to be partially insulated.

Thermal Decomposition Analysis of Sandwich Composites

Decomposition of the polymer matrix to the skins and to the organic core was assumed to occur via single-stage reaction processes. The decomposition reaction rate can be defined by the rate of density change to the skins or core ($d\rho/dt$) due to mass loss caused by the conversion of solid organic material to volatiles. When the skins and core decompose via a single-stage decomposition process then the density change rate can be expressed using the Arrhenius relationship:

$$\text{Skins } \frac{d\rho_{(s)}}{dt} = -(\rho_{v(s)} - \rho_{d(s)}) \left[\frac{\rho - \rho_{d(s)}}{\rho_{v(s)} - \rho_{d(s)}} \right]^n A_{(s)} e^{-(Q_{(s)}/RT)} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Core } \frac{d\rho_{(c)}}{dt} = -(\rho_{v(c)} - \rho_{d(c)}) \left[\frac{\rho - \rho_{d(c)}}{\rho_{v(c)} - \rho_{d(c)}} \right]^n A_{(c)} e^{-(Q_{(c)}/RT)} \quad (4)$$

n and A are the reaction order constant and pre-exponential factor, respectively. R is the universal gas constant. ρ , ρ_v and ρ_d are the instantaneous density, original (virgin material) density and density of the decomposed material, respectively.

Gibson et al. [14] found that for laminates the onset of visible char formation occurs when the matrix density decreased by about 20%. That is, the decomposition process has advanced to the stage where the polymer network structure has started to break-down via chain scission reactions resulting in 20% of the mass being converted to volatiles. Gibson and colleagues found empirically that when this occurs, the matrix has the visible blackness characteristic of charring, even though it has not completely decomposed.

During this criterion, the thermal model (Eq. 1) is used to compute the temperatures at many points through-the-thickness of the sandwich composite for increasing increments of heating time. When the local temperature at any point is sufficiently high to cause a 20% reduction to the density of the polymer matrix to the skins using Eq. 3 or to the core with Eq. 4 then charring is assumed to have started. By solving these equations for increasing increments of heating time it is possible to calculate the initiation and growth of the char zone in a sandwich composite until it is completely charred.

Post-Fire Mechanical Property Analysis of Sandwich Composites

Models have been formulated by Mouritz and colleagues [10,13] to calculate the post-fire stiffness and strength of fibre-polymer laminates. The models treat the fire-damaged composite as a two-layered material: one layer consisting of thermally decomposed (char) material and the other layer being pristine laminate. This modelling framework is applied here to calculate the post-fire mechanical properties of sandwich composites.

Post-Fire Modulus of Sandwich Composites

The axial tensile and compressive modulus (E) of a sandwich composite without damage is determined using:

$$E = \frac{E_{s,1}t_{s,1} + E_{s,2}t_{s,2} + E_c t_c}{t} \quad (5)$$

The subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the front (heated) and back skins, respectively. E_s and E_c is the original Young's modulus of the skin or core, respectively. t_s , t_c and t are the thickness of the skin, core and sandwich composite, respectively.

When it is assumed that the elastic modulus of any portion of the skins and core are reduced due to charring and that the strain across the load-bearing section of the sandwich composite is uniform, then the post-fire modulus is determined using:

$$E_{pf} = \left[E_{s1} \frac{(t_{s1} - t_{s1(char)})}{t_{s1}} + E_{s(char)} \frac{t_{s1(char)}}{t_{s1}} \right] + \left[E_{s2} \frac{(t_{s2} - t_{s2(char)})}{t_{s2}} + E_{s(char)} \frac{t_{s2(char)}}{t_{s2}} \right] + \left[E_c \frac{(t_c - t_{c(char)})}{t_c} + E_{c(char)} \frac{t_{c(char)}}{t_{s2}} \right] \quad (6)$$

$t_{s1(char)}$, $t_{s2(char)}$ and $t_{c(char)}$ are the thicknesses of the char region in the front skin, back skin and core, respectively. $E_{s(char)}$ and $E_{c(char)}$ are the modulus values for the charred skin and core, respectively. In cases when the post-fire modulus is dominated by the heated skin, then Eqn 6 reduces to:

$$E_{pf} \approx \left[E_{s1} \frac{(t_{s1} - t_{s1(char)})}{t_{s1}} + E_{s(char)} \frac{t_{s1(char)}}{t_{s1}} \right] \quad (7)$$

Post-Fire Tensile Strength of Sandwich Composites

Following fire exposure and when it is assumed that the tensile strength of any portion of the skins or core is reduced when the material decomposes to char, then the post-fire tensile failure stress of the sandwich composite (σ_{pf}) can be approximated using:

$$\sigma_{T, pf} = \left[\sigma_{T, s1} \frac{(t_{s1} - t_{s1(char)})}{t_{s1}} + \sigma_{T, s1(char)} \frac{t_{s1(char)}}{t_{s1}} \right] + \left[\sigma_{T, s2} \frac{(t_{s2} - t_{s2(char)})}{t_{s2}} + \sigma_{T, s2(char)} \frac{t_{s2(char)}}{t_{s2}} \right] + \left[\sigma_{T, c} \frac{(t_c - t_{c(char)})}{t_c} + \sigma_{T, c(char)} \frac{t_{c(char)}}{t_{s,2}} \right] \quad (8)$$

The subscript T refers to tension. $\sigma_{T,s}$ and $\sigma_{T,c}$ are the tensile failure stress values for the skin and core without fire damage, and $\sigma_{T,s(char)}$ and $\sigma_{T,c(char)}$ are the tensile failure stress values for the charred skin and core.

Post-Fire Compressive Strength of Sandwich Composites

The post-fire compressive failure stress of a sandwich composite is dependent on the failure mode, which can involve global buckling, core shear failure, skin failure, or skin wrinkling. Therefore, the mechanical model used to compute the post-fire compressive stress depends on the compressive failure mode. In this paper, only buckling failure is considered, and this occurs when the skins are thin and the core is thick and when the length of the sandwich composite is much greater than its thickness.

When it is assumed that any portion of the skins or core which have decomposed to char have no residual compressive stiffness, then the post-fire buckling load (P_{pf}) can be determined using:

$$P_{C, pf} = 4\pi^2 E_c b (t - t_c) \left[\frac{0.2887(t - t_{(char)})}{L} \right]^2 \quad (9)$$

E_c is the original compressive modulus of the sandwich composite without fire damage. b and L are the width and length of the sandwich composite, respectively. (In the experimental work reported later, L is the length over which the sandwich composite was exposed to the thermal flux). In the case that compressive failure is controlled solely by Euler buckling of the fire-damaged skin, Eqn. 9 is expressed by:

$$P_{C, pf} = 4\pi^2 E_c b (t_{s1} - t_c) \left[\frac{0.2887(t_{s1} - t_{(char)})}{L} \right]^2 \quad (10)$$

From this equation, the compressive buckling stress is simply calculated:

$$\sigma_{C, pf} = \frac{P_{C, pf}}{bt_{s1}} \quad (11)$$

3 MATERIALS AND FIRE STRUCTURAL TESTING

3.1 Sandwich Composite

The accuracy of the model in the calculation of the post-fire mechanical properties was assessed using a sandwich composite consisting of thin skins made of E-glass/vinyl ester laminate covering a thick core of balsa wood. The skins were made from E-glass plain woven fabric (830 g/m², Colan Industries) and vinyl ester resin (Derakane 411-350). The glass fabric was stacked in a cross-ply pattern with the warp tows aligned in the same direction. The liquid resin was brushed on to the fabric, and the skins were then consolidated using a vacuum bag until the matrix had cured. The skins were 1.7 mm thick and had a fibre volume content of about 44%.

The core was Baltek[®] SB structural end-grain balsa with an average density of ~150 kg/m³ and thickness of 6 mm. The balsa grains were aligned in the through-thickness direction of the sandwich

composite. The average density of the balsa was 150 kg/m^3 , although there is a large amount of variability (standard deviation $\sim 45 \text{ kg/m}^3$) within a single panel. The initial moisture content of the balsa wood was about 8%. The core was bonded to the skins using vinyl ester resin.

3.2 Simulated Fire Exposure

The sandwich composite was exposed to one-sided radiant heating that is representative of one possible fire scenario. A 100 mm long section of the front skin was exposed directly to an electric heater that radiated an initial constant thermal flux of 35 kW/m^2 for different times up to 20 minutes, at which point the sandwich composite was completely decomposed. The surface temperatures of the two skins were recorded continuously using thermocouples during exposure to the thermal flux.

3.3 Post-Fire Property Testing

Following heating, the sandwich composite samples were cooled to room temperature and the extent of decomposition and post-fire mechanical properties were measured. The post-fire tensile stiffness and strength was measured by axially loading the sandwich composite at an extension rate of 2 mm/min to failure using a 250 kN MTS machine operated at 20°C . The post-fire compressive testing involved axially compressing the composite sample at an end shortening rate of 0.5 mm/min to failure. The ends of sandwich composite were clamped, and the relatively high unsupported length-to-thickness ratio (approximately 50-to-1) caused the sample to deform and fail by buckling. The post-fire modulus was determined using a 25 mm long extensometer attached to the back face of the sandwich composite.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect of heating time on the temperature of the sandwich composite exposed to the thermal flux is shown in Figure 1. The data points show the temperatures measured using thermocouples located at the heated (front) skin, middle of the balsa core, and unheated (back) skin. The temperature of the front skin increased rapidly with exposure time to the thermal flux before reaching near thermal equilibrium after about 500 s. There was a large thermal gradient between the front and back surfaces ($\Delta T \sim 200\text{-}250^\circ\text{C}$) due mainly to the low thermal conductivity of the balsa core. This reveals that the core plays an important role in insulating the back skin, and this has significant influence on the post-fire properties as shown later.

Figure 1: Temperature-time profiles at the front (heated) skin, middle of the balsa core, and back skin of the sandwich composite exposed to the thermal flux. The curves and data points are the calculated and measured temperatures, respectively.

The solid curves in Figure 1 show the temperatures calculated with the thermal model (Eq. 1). The thermal and physical property data for the laminate skins and balsa wood given in Table 1 were used to solve the model. The thermal model provided a good, but not precise, calculation of the temperatures. The discrepancy between the calculated and measured temperatures is attributed to several assumptions with the thermal model. It is assumed that volatile flow is one-dimensional in the through-thickness direction whereas in the samples the gases also flow from the edges. The model also assumes that fire-induced damage such as blistering and debonding at the skin-core interface together with microscopic voids and cracks within the skins do not affect the internal temperatures, although experimental work shows they can alter significantly the heat conduction rate [1].

A plot of the effect of thermal flux exposure time on the percentage thickness of the sandwich composite which had thermally decomposed to char is shown in Figure 2. The char thickness increased rapidly with time up to ~600 seconds, beyond which both skins and the entire core had completely decomposed to char. The data points are the measured percent char thickness values and the curve was calculated using the thermal decomposition model, assuming that char formation occurs when the mass fraction of organic material in the sandwich composite is reduced by 20% (Eqns 3 & 4). Agreement between the measured and calculated char thickness values is good, although the model slightly under-predicted the extent of charring for short times (under ~200 seconds). The char predictions are sensitive to the calculated temperatures through-the-thickness of the sandwich composite. The thermal model (Eqns. 1 and 2) gave a good, but not precise, prediction of the temperatures (Fig. 1) and this would account for the differences between the measured and calculated char thickness values.

Figure 2: Effect of thermal flux exposure time on the percentage thickness of the sandwich composite which has thermally decomposed to char. The data points and curve show the measured and calculated char thickness values, respectively. The relative thicknesses of the face skins and core are indicated.

The effect of increasing exposure time to the thermal flux on the post-fire tensile modulus and strength properties of the sandwich composite is shown in Figure 3. The data points show the measured post-fire property values, and as expected these decreased with increasing time. The curves show the calculated post-fire tensile properties. Curves are shown for the loss in stiffness and strength due to the entire sandwich composite (solid curve) and the heated front skin (dashed curve). The analysis predicts rapid tensile softening and weakening of the heated skin, and this was due to the fast heating rate when exposed to the high thermal flux (as shown in Figure 1). The experimental post-fire stiffness and strength properties decreased at a much slower rate than predicted due to softening and weakening of the heated skin alone, and this was because the back skin retains its tensile properties for longer times due to the insulating effect of the balsa core. The post-fire tensile properties for the sandwich composite calculated using Eqns 6 and 8 (solid curve) agree reasonably well with the measured values, although the calculated stiffness was lower due presumably to an under-estimation in

the tensile modulus of the charred skins. The model also predicted that the post-fire tensile properties are constant between ~150 and 450 seconds, and this was because the front skin had decomposed but the back skin has not yet weakened significantly due to the thermal lag effect of the core. This demonstrates the important role of the core in the post-fire tensile properties of sandwich composites.

Figure 4 shows the effect of increasing thermal flux exposure time on the post-fire compressive modulus and strength. The data points show the measured properties and the dashed and solid curves show the calculated post-fire properties when it is assumed that compressive failure occurs by the sandwich composite buckling (Eqn 10) and front skin buckling (Eqn 9), respectively. The model accurately predicted the post-fire properties when it was assumed that charring of the front skin controls the post-fire stiffness and failure stress, and the back skin has no significant influence. The model provided a reasonable prediction of the post-fire compressive properties, although it was not highly precise because small errors in the calculation of the char thickness translate into large errors in the post-fire buckling stress for the front skin because $\sigma_{C, pf} \propto \alpha(t_{s1} - t_{s1(char)})^2$. The results in Figure 4 also show that the post-fire compression properties decreased at a much faster rate than the tension properties. The results also reveal that the thermal protection provided by the core to the back skin, which is important for tension loading, is not significant for compression.

Figure 3: Effect of thermal flux exposure time on the post-fire tensile modulus and failure stress. The data points and curves show the measured and calculated post-fire properties, respectively.

Figure 4: Effect of thermal flux exposure time on the post-fire compressive modulus and failure stress. The data points and curves show the measured and calculated post-fire properties, respectively.

The validated thermal-mechanical model can be used to perform parametric analysis of the post-

fire properties of sandwich composites following exposure to different fires scenarios. For example, Figure 5 shows the effect of increasing thermal flux on the calculated post-fire tensile and compressive failure stresses of the sandwich material. As expected, the post-fire properties decreased with increasing thermal flux, and this was due to the higher heating rates and higher temperatures causing faster burn-through of the composite. The analysis reveals that the thermal flux exposure time needed to reduce the post-fire tensile stress increases rapidly when the thermal flux is reduced, and at the lowest thermal flux (10 kW/m²) the failure stresses remain relatively high because of the slow decomposition rates of the front skin and core. This analysis also reveals that the insulating effect of the core in protecting the back skin becomes more pronounced at lower thermal fluxes. In contrast, the influence of thermal flux on the post-fire compressive failure stress is less marked except for the lowest flux, when the temperature is sufficiently low that it takes a long time before the front skin has thermally decomposed enough to fail by buckling.

Figure 5: Analysis showing the influence of the radiant thermal flux on the post-fire tensile and compression failure stresses of the sandwich composite.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A validated model for calculating the post-fire mechanical properties of sandwich composites at room temperature has been developed. The model computes the temperatures in the through-thickness direction of the composite when exposed for increasing times to the thermal flux representative of the heat radiate by a fire. Based on the temperatures, the initiation and growth of the decomposition (char) zone through the composite can be calculated. Mechanical models are then used to compute the residual stiffness and strength properties based on the amount of decomposition to the skins and core.

The numerical accuracy of the model was assessed using a sandwich composite material consisting of woven E-glass/vinyl ester laminate skins and balsa wood core. The thermal model can predict the temperatures, the decomposition model can estimate char formation, and the mechanical model can compute the post-fire tensile and compressive properties with good accuracy. It is envisaged that the model can be used to assess the residual structural integrity of burnt sandwich composite structures following fire exposure.

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